

IMPROVED PHOTOMETRIC CORRECTION OF SELENE MULTIBAND IMAGER DATA FOR MARE IMBRIUM TO EVALUATE LAVA FLOW THICKNESSES. K. Toyokawa^{1,2}, H. Hiesinger², C.H. van der Bogert², N. Schmedemann², W. Iqbal², L. Wueller², A. Gao^{2,3}, M.N. Yamashita¹, and T. Morota¹, ¹Department of Earth and Planetary Science, The University of Tokyo (toyokawa@eps.s.u-tokyo.ac.jp); ²Institut für Planetologie, Universität Münster; ³School of Earth Sciences, China University of Geosciences

Introduction: Mare Imbrium is one of the largest and most geologically important mare basins on the Moon, which preserves a long and complex record of mare volcanism [1, 2]. Clarifying the distribution, sequence, and thickness of individual lava flows in this basin is essential for understanding the temporal evolution of lunar volcanism and the thermal history of the Moon. In particular, the thickness distribution of lava flows provides key constraints on the stratigraphy of mare basalts and temporal changes in eruption magnitudes. Schaber (1973) [3] estimated that the mean thickness of Eratosthenian lava flows in Mare Imbrium is ~30 m. However, evaluating flow thickness at the scale of individual flow units remains challenging because it requires compositional data to investigate materials exposed from underlying layers, typically at sub-kilometer scale. High-spatial-resolution spectral data offer a promising way to address this problem. The SELENE Multiband Imager (MI) acquired visible and near-infrared images of the lunar surface at spatial resolutions suitable for investigating compositional variations within individual lava flow units [4].

In this study, we aim to reveal the thickness distribution of lava flows in Mare Imbrium using MI data with high spatial resolution. As a first step toward this goal, we focus on generating photometrically corrected MI products that are valid at sub-kilometer-scale and evaluating spectral parameters that can distinguish lava-flow units. These products form the basis for subsequent crater-based thickness analysis of lava-flow units and stratigraphic reconstruction.

Methods: To evaluate the thickness distribution of lava flows, we follow a workflow consisting of four steps: (1) data processing, (2) mapping lava-flow units, (3) identifying craters that excavate and do not excavate buried lava units, and (4) estimating the thickness of each lava unit.

The first step is photometric correction of SELENE MI observations. Because a subsequent step requires identifying sub-kilometer-scale craters that expose underlying materials, reducing topography- and illumination-driven brightness variations is essential. We therefore applied photometric correction to MI data [5] in Mare Imbrium using the high-resolution digital elevation model SLDEM2015 [6] (~60 m/pixel at the equator), in order to produce spectrally and spatially consistent data products suitable for detailed geological interpretation.

The second step is mapping lava-flow units using spectral information derived from the corrected MI data. For this purpose, we calculated several spectral indices that are expected to reflect compositional and mineralogical differences among mare basalts. These indices include FeO and TiO₂ abundances [7], as well as band asymmetry and peak wavelength [8] of the 1 μm absorption band (Fig. 2). We examine whether these indices emphasize flow boundaries or internal variability clearly.

The third and fourth steps use impact craters to constrain lava-flow thickness and stratigraphy. In the third step, we identify craters that either excavate underlying material or remain confined within the surface unit. In the fourth step, we use the depths of these excavating and non-excavating craters to derive minimum and maximum thickness constraints for each lava flow, and integrate these constraints with the mapped flow-unit distribution to estimate unit thicknesses and reconstruct stratigraphic relationships [9].

Results: Figure 1 illustrates the FeO abundance distribution derived from our photometric correction (Fig. 1(a)) at a sub-kilometer-scale crater in Mare Imbrium, compared with that of the previously published MI-MAP product (Fig. 1(b)) [10]. It demonstrates that our photometrically corrected MI data reduce topography-related artifacts and reveal fine-scale spectral variations relevant to geological interpretation. Therefore, it provides a strong foundation for evaluating sub-kilometer-scale compositional distributions.

Figure 1. Comparison of FeO distributions derived from (a) our improved photometrically corrected MI data and (b) the previously published MI product. Panel (c) shows FeO abundance profiles along the lines indicated in (a) and (b).

Figure 2 shows the FeO and TiO₂ distributions and the spectral asymmetry map for Mare Imbrium. It highlights variations that are not always expressed clearly in standard compositional indicators alone such as FeO and TiO₂. Because the distribution of spectral asymmetry is different from those of FeO and TiO₂, it can be used as another independent index to distinguish lava-flow units.

Figure 2. Colorized maps of Mare Imbrium showing (a) FeO, (b) TiO₂, and (c) band asymmetry of the 1- μ m absorption band.

These results are important because reliable unit mapping is the key prerequisite for crater-based thickness evaluation. The newly corrected MI products not only improve the spectral fidelity of the dataset but also enhance the interpretability of small-scale geological features relevant to volcanic stratigraphy. The combination of high-resolution photometrically corrected imagery and multiple spectral indices therefore provides a practical basis for identifying discrete lava units and preparing for quantitative thickness analysis.

Conclusions: We developed a workflow to evaluate the thickness distribution of lava flows in Mare Imbrium using high-resolution spectral data obtained by SELENE MI. As the first outcome of this framework, we generated newly photometrically corrected MI data and used them to examine spectral parameters for lava-flow mapping. The corrected data improve the visibility of compositional and spectral heterogeneities at sub-kilometer scales, and our results indicate that spectral asymmetry is diagnostic for distinguishing lava-flow units in Mare Imbrium.

These findings demonstrate that high-resolution, photometrically corrected spectral data provide an effective basis for resolving individual mare lava units and for advancing thickness evaluation based on impact-crater excavation. In the presentation, we

will further discuss the distribution of excavating crater depths and the estimated thicknesses of lava-flow units derived from this framework.

References: [1] Hiesinger et al. (2000) *JGR*, 105, 29,239–29,275. [2] Wu et al. (2025) *PSJ*, 6, 141. [3] Schaber (1973) *In: Proc. of 4th LPSC*, 1, 73–92 [4] Haruyama J. et al. (2008) *EPS*, 60, 243–255. [5] Toyokawa and Yamashita (2026) *LPSC 2026*, Abstract #1086. [6] Barker M. K. et al. (2016) *Icarus*, 273, 346–355. [7] Otake H. et al. (2012) , *LPSC 2012*, Abstract #1905. [8] Horgan et al. (2014) *Icarus* 234, 132–154. [9] Chen et al. (2018) *JGR Planets*, 123, 630–645. [10] Ohtake M. et al. (2013) *Icarus*, 226, 364–374.